

The Paradox In The Poetry Of Ibn Zaydun Al-Andalus

Munir Obaid Najm

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 27, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: October 30, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Paradox, Ibn Zaydun Al-Andalus, Lisan al-Arab</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7337994</p>	<p><i>Paradox is a literary practice that has a long history that extends back to the early literary ages. Hence, we will stand on some of its definitions and limits, in line with the nature of our research, and the way in which we will address the concept of paradox in Ibn Zaydun's poetry.</i></p> <p><i>Language paradox</i></p> <p><i>It came in Lisan al-Arab: The difference between the thing is a difference and a separation: its statement (1). Paradox in the language means differentiation and difference, and the word did not appear in the Holy Qur'an in this capacity and meaning. (Its material is found in the Qur'an, but without a thousand shares)</i></p> <p><i>Paradox in terminology</i></p> <p><i>Paradox is one of the critical terms about which there has been much controversy in the past and the present. As it included many new aspects, its definitions differed according to different scholars, how they understood them, the nature of the studied poetic production, and the research requirements it imposed on the student.</i></p>

Introduction

In fact, the paradox did not exist in our heritage as a well-known term that has its foundations and rules as in the West, but there are many critical and rhetorical terms that approach the concept of paradox, including: counterpoint, pun, sarcasm, praise with something similar to slander and others. Dr. comments. Nasser Shabana regarding the existence of paradox as a term in the Arab heritage or not, saying, "Whether this term exists or does not exist, the matter is the same, as the matter is not dependent on its existence or non-existence. The dependence is on whether the concept or rhetorical type to which the paradox refers in its modern sense is present in the heritage or not. No" (2), for he believes that searching for the spirit of paradox is more beneficial than searching for a garment that may change from time to time.

The concept of paradox among Western critics

Many studies have attracted the paradox as one of the epistemological concepts that different fields (philosophical, social and literary) dispute, but the paradox dates back to its first appearance among Westerners to the Greek word *eironia*, which was brought by Plato in his republic and Socrates called one of his victims (3) The paradox arose in a Western origin, shrouded in ambiguity, indeterminacy and openness to more than one concept. (Miouk) is the most prominent contemporaries who considered the concept of paradox, who sees that paradox no longer means today what it meant in previous eras, nor does it mean in a particular country everything that can be It means in another country, and it does not mean in the street everything it means in the classroom or to a researcher as it means it to another researcher (4), and he tried to simplify and shorten its definition, so he went to the fact that the paradox is the art of saying something without saying it in reality (5), meaning that we are in the paradox We arrive at an understanding of the intended meaning, not through what the word indicates, but rather by what lies in the word that was said from a meaning that the saying did not indicate. The German critic August Schlegel sees paradox as a form of contradiction (6), and the well-known critic Richards emphasized this contradictory essence when he was discussing the subject of fiction in his book (Principles of Literary Criticism) (7)

The paradox of modern Arab critics

The Arab critics in the modern era knew the paradox, influenced by what came in the West of visions and studies, and the follower of the opinions of the modern Arab critics finds them agreeing on the fact that contradiction is the main condition for the paradox and the pillar on which it rests in the most general (8). It is obvious that the literary work has two levels of expression The superficial level of speech and the deep level that the reader discovers in the literary text through a stylistic stimulus raised by the writer, represented by the method of contrast, which means the opposite of the connotation, which Dr. Richards says in his definition of the paradox as representing the balance of opposites (10), the meaning that is given in the paradox is intended to be discovered by the reader that the paradox is in the words of Dr. Nabila Ibrahim is "a skillful and intelligent linguistic game between the two parties of the writer and the reader" (11) The writer or the maker of the paradox carries the text in the paradox, leaving behind the means of communication for the reader who discovers the paradox based on his experience in reading the text, which was also confirmed by Dr. Abd al-Hadi Khudair said

that the paradox “is to provoke the reader and stimulate his mind to go beyond the apparent contradictory meaning of the phrase and reach the hidden meanings” (12). The important role of the reader, who depends on his sense of knowledge, the nature of his understanding and his literary taste, remains in knowing the relationship of antagonism that exists in the elements of literary work.

A look at the life of IbnZaydun al-Andalus..... Paradox of events

He is Abu Al-Walid Ahmed bin Abdullah bin Ahmed bin Zaydun Al-Makhzumi, his family’s origin is from BanuMakhzoom from Quraysh (13) He was born in Rusafa, Cordoba, in the house of knowledge, esteem and wealth in the year (394 - 1003 AD), so he began receiving knowledge from his father, and he was a jurist and judge from the media of the Maliki sect (14). He is famous for his brilliance, knowledge and literature, and when his father died in Al-Bireh in the year 450 AH, his grandfather assigned him to his mother, the judge Abu Bakr Muhammad bin Ibrahim al-Qaisi (355 AH)

The reader examining the life of IbnZaydun al-Andalus finds it divided into two prominent thresholds, or in other words, two paradoxes, the first of which is the external / general modernity that the poet passed through in the midst of life. As for the first threshold / the first paradox, it came in three phases, or if it is correct to express three paradoxes:

The first stage (the first paradox) of his life in the court of Bani Johor (422-442.)e)

When the matter of the Umayyads in Cordoba was disturbed before the final fall of the caliphate, and Hisham the third fled from it in the year (422 AH) Abu Al-HazmJahour bin Muhammad was his minister (16), the people of Cordoba feared the consequences of the turmoil and chaos, and they found in Abi Al-Hazm bin Jahour a powerful ruler, so they obeyed him. Al-Madina, IbnZaydun contacted the emerging state early and appointed Abu Al-Hazm the head of a consultancy ministry, not a ministry of labor. Abu Al-Hazm and IbnZaydun were friends before, then IbnZaydun had political hopes, and now the opportunity to reach something of them has been spurred on by the winds of politics throwing IbnZaydun into the current of public life, including There were rivalries and intrigues (17). IbnZaydun and his opponents were much envious inside and outside the court of IbnJahour. The most antagonistic of them to him and the most influential among them was the Minister Abu Amer bin Abdus. IbnZaydun wrote his serious letter in which he tried to degrade the position of IbnAbdus in the eyes of the birth of the daughter of al-Mustaqfi who would come. He mentioned it later when he listed the faults of IbnAbdus, which made the latter attach to IbnZaydun accusations, including that he was inclined to return the Umayyad rule, a charge that was common at the time (18). In the life of IbnZaydun, after he was a minister, he became A captive in the darkness of prison, this incident was severe in his life, which left the most impact on himself, as it made him taste the bitterness of humiliation after the height of power and the pain of misery after the bliss of happiness. To sympathize with Abu Al-Hazm’s heart, so Abu Al-Walid bin Abi Al-Hazm suggested to him that he escape from his prison, but he did not accept at first. , saying (20)

There is no shame, no shame in fleeing, for the Prophet of guidance fled to the cave

IbnZaydun went around Cordoba in disguise, then wrote a poem to his sheikh, Abu Bakr bin Muslim, complaining about his condition and asking for intercession to Abu al-Hazm, saying in it (21)

I don't think it's okay, hurts eternity and despair

Perhaps I oversaw one's hopes, Yass

So the intercession succeeded, and IbnZaydun would regain the approval of Abu al-Hazm, and the water would return to its streams, and IbnZaydun would regain his credentials in the court of the Johor family. The second stage (the second paradox) succeeded Abu Al-Waleed bin Jahour, his father, who died in the year (435 AH). He delegates him as an ambassador between him and the kings of the sects(22), and here the second paradox occurs. In an almost surprising and mysterious manner, a sluggishness occurs between the poet and his king. Perhaps one of the most prominent reasons is that a group of IbnZaydun’s companions made an attempt in Cordoba to re-invite the Umayyads, so IbnZaydun was afraid to return to Cordoba. So he went to

Seville, where the court of the Abadites (23)

The third journey (the third paradox) This stage begins in the court of BaniAbbad, as we find that Al-Mu'tadid bin Abbad approached IbnZaydun, and his life in the court of BaniAbbad went as good as he hoped, and he was appreciated in the city of Seville by its notables and lords. To him all the affairs of his state and the raising of the cost between him and the poet, and when Al-Mu'tadid realizes his death, his son Al-Mu'tamid succeeds him, and IbnZaydun takes over in his heart what he used to hold in his father's heart, rather he raised him to the zenith of his advice and ministry. IbnZaydun, when al-Mu'tamid sent a group of statesmen to calm the minds and put IbnZaydun among them, and IbnZaydun was sick, so al-Mu'tamidibnAbbad was excused, but he did not pardon him. 24) As a result, IbnZaydun became seriously ill as a result of that incident until he died in Seville in the year (463 AH) and his body was transferred to Cordoba and buried there (25) These three roles/paradoxes that affected the poet's life made his poetry buzz with many colors of paradoxes filtering from the circumstances and circumstances he went through.

The second threshold (the second paradox) is his love for the birth of the daughter of Al-Mustaqfi, which is one of the most important events in IbnZaydun’s life, until it filled more than two-thirds of his hair. She was clever, polite in arts and manners, strong in character, unlike her father, the Caliph al-Mustaqfi, who was an ignorant

man with weak will and opinion, immersed in amusement, disregarding him. Since he is still famous for drinking and unemployment, he is sick of secret and openly, captive of lust..." (27)

And when al-Mustakfi was killed in the year (416 AH), her birth escaped from the moral and social constraints, and her house was made a forum for men of literature, and she turned to many reasons for amusement, IbnBassam says. 28) The individual poets and writers are decimated by the sweetness of her companionship and the ease of her veil. During this period, IbnZaydun was among those who differed to her council and remained persistent in that for days and felt that she affected him on others, so she fell in his heart as it fell in her heart, and the two lovers blessed with days and nights famous among people, photographed by IbnZaydun In his poetry when he says (29)

**bid farewell to loving patience, and leave you with its secret entrusted to you
He knocks on the tooth if there is no provision in that hole, when he spreads you**

If the night is long after you, then how often do I complain about the shortness of the night with you?

The meeting was repeated in the gardens of Cordoba, and the world smiled for the two lovers, and IbnZaydun began photographing his happiness What is overwhelming in more than one place in his poetry (30) However, this love, which began early and then ignited with the utmost speed, did not live in its purity and loyalty for long and began to fade as quickly as it had been raised with. Pain throughout his life dyed his hair in all kinds of paradoxes. The heart of Walad changed the direction of IbnZaydun's heart and turned the back of the shield for him. This is due to several reasons, which we summarize as follows:

1-Born was a playful woman with a moody, flabby mood, and for this reason she did not enjoy her full love from any of the admirers, influential in all of this, to live her life according to her will and desire, influenced by the chaotic life with which her family was known, for she was famous for two houses that she organized and embroidered on both sides of her dress.

**I, by God, are good for His Excellency, and I walk my walk, and I come lost
I can take my lover from my cheek plate and give my kiss to whoever desires it**

2-She gave birth to a good-natured, well-played black slave girl named Utbah. She sang one night and IbnZaidan was impressed by her performance, which prompted him to get excited and repeat the melody, so the loving woman moved others. and bitterness when it says (32)

If you were fair in the love between us, you would not be my maidservant, and you would not have any choice

**You left a branch bearing its beauty, and drifted towards the branch that did not bear fruit
And you knew that I was the moon of heaven, but you went to my apartment with the buyer**

3-The meeting of AbiAmer bin Abdus with the birth of the daughter of Al-Mustaqfi, who had been assigned to her, hoping to win her love. Although this message spread among the writers who began to ponder what IbnZaydun narrated in it from the faults of IbnAbdus, his birth was not affected by this new method and it turned his direction sharply and increased from it, so it is neither tenderness for the old lover nor did she flee from the new lover, and IbnAbdus turned on IbnAbdus style Zaydun set this and plots against him and accused him of colluding with the Cordoba government (33), and the plot succeeded and the elegant poet was thrown into prison, and thus his relationship ended with a birth at the end of his life. IbnZaydun felt that he studied it on two axes:

First: Paradox as a tool for expressing love with the birth of Al-Mustakfi's daughter

It can be said that the paradox is a rich method that allows the poet/text producer to choose between a number of tools to establish his poetic image and draw its features with the accuracy that the poet believes is capable of tensing the language to reach the significance of the paradox. His quest to reach his poetic purposes, since he devoted a lot of his time and poetic achievement to the birth of Al-Mustakfi's daughter, he must be aware of the fact that birth is able without more trouble to touch and understand what he wants to say, explicitly or insinuatingly, because the addressee / the lover is also a poet and in this In particular, the researcher sees that IbnZaydun's tendency to paradox, whether in its linguistic form or through the connotations transmitted through declaration and allusion, is supported by his knowledge of the ability of the addressee to understand the implications of paradox, especially if we know that the paradox requires mental effort and deep meditation to reach the contradiction and reveal the connotations of contradiction between The apparent meaning, meaning and the mysterious hidden in the depths of the text and its distant spaces, so IbnZaydun included the paradox style in his poetry for the birth of the daughter of Al-Mustaqfi in order to create the semantic tension in the poem through the contradiction in In order to portray to the recipient / the birth of the daughter of Al-Mustakfi first, and the general recipients second, the greatness of the surgeries and contradictory attitudes he feels that reveal his love story for this princess poet.

This is what we see clearly in his saying (34)

Absent from me, and present with me! I call to you, when my patience grows old, so listen

Do I have the right to be wretched with your love, or to see my breath on fire, drowning in my tears?

The researcher believes that the poet in more than one place is betting on the problem of presence and absence, as we find him sometimes making a confrontation through language between these two antagonists. The

paradox may refer to the first beginnings of exploiting the connotations resulting from the problem of presence and absence. The presence of a birth necessarily means for the poet life with its bliss and joys, while absence only generates burning breaths and drowning tears, while we encounter in this place another type of paradox formed by the poet's rise – and in order to He demonstrates the depth of his emotional experience by drawing an interview between two antagonists that philosophers have always referred to, namely water and fire. If we realize that each of these antagonisms dissolves with the existence of the other, the poet, through the method of paradox, has combined them in an aesthetic equation whose two ends are (burning breath) and (drowning in tears)

At other times we encounter the poet saying (35)

O soon, when he is far away, present, when he is absent!

As if he is aware with his poetic / psychological sense of the importance and feasibility of capturing the meaning that leads to the paradox by shedding light on the linguistic and semantic contradiction between the two problems of proximity and distance, presence and absence, which we referred to in the previous place, as the researcher sees that the poet's use of semantic logic whose features draw the problem of presence and absence in a way Repeated evidence of the text producer's awareness of the importance of the paradox method to create the largest possible amount of verbal astonishment and then reach the attention of the person to whom a speech is addressed (birth) and See both to what the poet wants to say. The student of the course of the love relationship between IbnZaydun and the birth of the daughter of Al-Mustaqfi, which, according to the researchers' agreement, represents an important threshold of the threshold of the Arab love journey, will find that this relationship has witnessed some paradoxes on the life level, and the researcher believes that the poet may have sought her to send a message to the birth stating sympathy or Blasphemy or the desire to increase the affinity and among these paradoxes is his quest to love (threshold) one of his birth attendants, as we see the poet and his love with that girl tends greatly to use the method of paradox, where the researcher sees that this method chosen by the poet is the closest actually to the overall atmosphere of that spinning story He says (36)

**The memory of passion came back after forgetting, and the heart created longing after solace
From the love of a slave girl, who has an idol made of lujain, on which is the crown of an aqiyan**

So that the one I loved would have a conclusion, I abrogated, in her love, an unbeliever with faith

In this place, we see the poet betting on the meaning generated by the events of a linguistic approach between a group of antonyms such as (remembrance / forgetting, longing / solace, infidelity / faith), where we find IbnZaydun, the Muslim poet, daring to use the concept of naskh with Quranic connotations to produce his formation characterized by the highest Degrees of paradox, his proximity to the threshold of the slave girl and his distance from birth represent for him what indicates the abandonment of disbelief with its ideological and linguistic connotations to the faith that hoards those connotations. It is based on a problem that represents in itself a paradox in the history of Arab thought. To demonstrate the logicity of what the researcher mentioned, we can reflect on IbnZaydun's saying (37)

O soul, go to him, for my heart has no creed for it.

Sterilized with a drop of amber on its golden cheek

Forget me to repent from his love when the sun rises from the West

In this place, we can clearly see the inclination of IbnZaydun to weave his artistic image in the light of a poetic language with ideological connotations. The poet's sun may rise from Morocco, which makes him lose the opportunity of the desired repentance, which the poet refers to at the beginning of this piece with the sentence "O soul" that invites to go to the beloved. (Oh soul / Repentance / the rising of the sun from Morocco) And in a piece of material "would fate be given to IbnZaydun" he says (38)

O shameful branch, if it is dangerous, and shameful bribery and bribery if they look

A lover redeemed me, his affair is astonishing, you did not come with a sin but he came as an apology

What I sensed of caution did not save me from you. The plot of desire consumes caution

What was your love, sedition was decreed, can the boy push the fate?

This piece, which is characterized by wonderful musical elegies, represents the poet's desire to try another type of paradox, this time based on presenting an amazing picture to the reader, who must then discover through the intended meaning what the poet intends to convey. Her beauty is ashamed, even the young twigs declare that his beloved is forcing him, because of her kindness and gentleness, to take the initiative in apologizing, despite the fact that she is the one who committed the guilt. The matter is how not, and that his love for his beloved is but a fitnah that fate wanted her to be, and can he pay for his destiny himself?

In a demonstration scene, IbnZaydun says (39)

And when we met to bid farewell in the morning, and in the courtyard of the palace, banners of

Antiques were tied, drums clapped, and signs of parting were visible.

We wept blood, until our eyes were running red tears, with scars in them.

And we used to beg the op, after three, so how about it, when she had extras!

We find the poet exerting himself through a skillful imaginative language in drawing a picture of his farewell to the birth of the daughter of al-Mustaqfi, where IbnZaydun completed the construction of his own semantic theater and brought to him all the audio and visual effects required by the scene. Sensitivity is represented in trying to market the idea of its conclusion that this meeting between the poet and his beloved, which was carefully prepared, is but the beginning of a long separation that there is no hope of ending. It is logical when the reader continues to follow the events that the mentioned poetic passage includes, leading to special apparent and inward connotations, and the researcher sees that the reader in this passage is the central focus that the poet intended to direct the message to. The contemplator of IbnZaydun's poetry will find it in the process of consolidating the recipient's convictions with a paradox schedule to pass the poetic purpose and consolidate it, whether in the field of meaning that is revealed to the eye or in the field of meaning that the reader must hunt, because he is proud of the ability of contrast / collision / paradox that results from the process of events of spatial juxtaposition between words inconsistent, and this is what we find evident in his saying:

How much of a heart have you broken? It is true that your eyelids are sick, healthy patients

When I hide love, my body describes it with its eloquent, mute, deaf tongues

In this witness, we find that IbnZaydun has produced a juxtaposition between the words (the sick / the righteous) as well as the words (the silence / the eloquence). Wellness, illness, and the concept of silence and fluency, we must be obligated to understand the poet's goals related to his desire to portray an atypical relationship with the birth of the daughter of Al-Mustakfi, as this non-stereotypical love necessitates for its portrayal a non-typical language that can produce in one form a poetic production that combines contradictions through the paradox method. Birth with beautiful eyelids nurses the healthy, healthy person. Just as we find the poet when he tries to hide his love, his body quickly utters the wondrous year of fatigue and wishful thinking, and that miraculous one allows the poet to describe it through the paradoxical style as mute and eloquent at the same time. In order for the researcher to demonstrate that the paradox represents a major role in determining IbnZaydun's choices and poetic purpose, we refer to his saying (41)

You laugh in love, and I weep, God, among us, judges

I say, when the hate flew away from me, a word with a meaning, his heart is wandering.

O sleeper, his love awakened me, grant me sleep, O sleeper!

In this piece in which the poet seeks to prove his birth, we find him this time revealing his poetic paradoxes in an easy and abstaining manner at the same time, after he had - in previous places - established these paradoxes in light of intellectual, ideological and subjective contexts we encounter here and he declares by addressing Birth that it As a lover, she is filled with laughter and savors as many delights and gentleness as she can, expressed in blissful sleep, while his share is weeping and mourning. Weeping, wailing, as usual, in most of the poets' love experiences, while the beloved, laughing and contented, enjoys that. As for the second reading, it is a linguistic reading that relies on creating an opposing link between two completely intersecting concepts, namely laughter, crying, sleep and sleep. If we agree that IbnZaydun has a deep poetic culture, then we We immediately realize that the irony was the poet's preferred choice to reach his poetic purpose.

Paradox as a tool for communicating with the political and social environment

Perhaps one of the important matters on which the researcher can pause, while studying the paradox as a method of poetic depiction, is the ability of the paradox to be a tool that allows the poet, through its reliance on antonyms and strangeness, to communicate what he wants to those who are addressed in a more realistic and quick way of impact, and this intent seems more It is clear when it comes to IbnZaydun's desire to convey messages to the princes, rulers and high people with the intention of getting close to them or obtaining their approval and obtaining their gifts and sympathy, especially since the poet has lived a turbulent life that forces him to knock on the door of the rulers and obtain their approval. Perhaps this intent seems clearer in IbnZaydun's saying, congratulating Caliph Al-Mu'tadid on the advent of the blessed Eid al-Adha, when he says (42)

Hell is for his sinners, whose fuel is ripe, and the Garden of Eden is for the obedient.

Here, IbnZaydun is inclined to appease the Caliph by leaving the impression that the poet is able, in a way that no one may compete with him, to depict the nature of the Caliph / the praised one, and to weave a picture of the mechanism by which the servants are deceived. And poetic at the same time, since the Caliph / Mamdouh will appear through the poetic image in two forms: the body of the disbeliever / hell and the body of the satisfied / the giver. Therefore, IbnZaydun finds that the paradox style meets what he wants, so he uses the terms (hell prepared for the disobedient versus the paradise gifted for the obedient) and this is the ideal use that does not It is devoid of intention to create a juxtaposition between antagonists that could facilitate the poet's task in gaining the approval of the Caliph and obtaining his gifts, and he is the one in control of the affairs of the servants, as the poet declares in his saying (43)

God watches over him one who is stubborn, with whom is the hand of eternity

hardening in his pleasure and merciful Al-Mutadid represents the hand of eternity that appears once while it is oppressive and hard and appears at another time in the dress of compassion, which is the meaning that IbnZaydun saw that the paradox through creating a confrontation between the concepts of (compassion and

cruelty) will be the most effective method in conveying the desired meaning. The researcher believes that the recipient of the poetic discourse must be more interactive with the texts that behave in exoticism/paradox as the best way to accomplish what it seeks to say. Perhaps this problem is still valid to the present time. In order to demonstrate the reality of what we went to, we encounter the poet in another place, and he employs the method of paradox again in addressing Al-Mu'tadid, this time in order to comfort him in his daughter who left in the prime of youth, as he says (44)

The secrets of eternity are worse than thanks and consolation

.....
I would like a bride to be buried, it was the gift

Here we can imagine that IbnZaydun was not the only one who mourned the daughter of the Caliph in that calamity, but he was among a number of poets who were trying to seize this opportunity to gain the approval of the Caliph and perhaps his gifts at that time. In describing the tragic scene experienced by the Caliph, which IbnZaydun likens to an age that harms and eases, as it does not prove in any case, as it can be joyful and dewy at a particular time, but it can be cruel and snatches what we love from our hands at any moment, IbnZaydun uses the paradox method and creates a sad image of the daughter of the Caliph, the bride who does not go to her husband's bedroom, but to the grave, which has become a substitute for the marital home. We see that this meaning cannot be consistent with the poet except through a smart and conscious use of the style. The irony will make the Caliph more able to touch him, and he is undoubtedly experiencing a psychological crisis resulting from the loss of what he loves. The researcher believes that IbnZaydun's closeness to al-Mu'tadid, which is confirmed by historical sources, which indicate that the two men had socially and politically contemporaneously for more than nine years, gave the poet the opportunity to get acquainted with closeness to the psychological and cultural mood of the Caliph, and this is what we found evident in the way in which the poet lamented Al-Mu'tadid's daughter. And we encounter him again in a different scene on the day that al-Mu'tadid ordered to oppose some of his poems, so we find the poet accomplishing his new task inclined to paradox as a method to reach the desired, which confirms, in our opinion, the poet's knowledge of the mood of his praise, not to mention that the nature of the era and the general cultural character prevailing in that era, which favors the easy and the impossible. From the saying, IbnZaydun says (45)

**Your closeness shortens my long night, and your peace heals my ailing heart
And if the wind of rebellions blew from you, I lost the breeze of life at night**

We find the poet here intending to astonish the recipient/caliph by inserting (shortness and length, healing and illness) in one scene as two opposing dualities that produce the meaning of paradox by intending to seek a specific meaning. The concept of length serves and the matter is repeated when the poet forms a paradox based on the duality of healing and illness, as that proximity to the Caliph is the means to heal the poet's ailing heart. The researcher believes that IbnZaydun is fully aware of the role of paradox in attracting the attention of the recipient, not only as a means of astonishment, but as a method of linguistic performance that allows the person to whom the speech is addressed to have a realistic opportunity to flip the issues presented by IbnZaydun on more than one face and then touch the indications and lessons that it can be found in each of them, and this, in our opinion, explains to a large extent IbnZaydun's insistence on including in his pieces and poems the largest possible number of contradictory concepts or those that negate each other. Among the rulers, princes, ministers and social elites in an attempt to get close to them and sympathize with them, including the poem that IbnZaydun sent from his prison addressing the minister Abu Hafs bin Burd in an attempt to sympathize with him, as he says (46)

**I don't think bass hurts eternity and yasoo
Perhaps someone oversaw one's hopes, despair
And may an omission save you and make you beware
Likewise, eternity, if people are not honored, people will be humiliated
And the sons of the days, brother, were rich and humble**

In this poem, IbnZaydun uses in an overflowing manner, with clear intention, several concepts and linguistic structures in which the recipient may see a clear contradiction. The Caliph Al-Mutadid, where it is used (to hurt / despair, in the sense of healing, hope / despair, omission / caution, honor / humiliation, joy / humiliation). With a simple examination of these concepts, we can identify two essential things. The first is the clear and blatant contradiction between each of them to the degree that it makes us realize the difficulty of the poet's task in achieving any form of approximation between them, whether at the linguistic or conceptual level. As for the second matter, it is the multiplicity of those uses on which the paradox is based in one poem. Available time. In another poem, we find IbnZaydun succeeds in entering the world of knowledge through another door, which is the paradox, which we can call the idea/knowledge paradox, as he praises the Caliph Abu Al-Hazm bin Jahour (47)

His consent is hostile and loyal, and in it he is punished and reprimanded.

In this place we see IbnZaydun pointing out that the Caliph is satisfied with all the loyalists and opponents alike, and this is a paradox in itself. From a paradox, although the concept of satisfaction refers to reward in the most

general, but the satisfaction of IbnJahour may include (reward and punishment), and this, in our opinion, is an example of a clear paradox that confirms IbnZaydun's interest in making his texts of an anxious nature that alerts the recipient to the messages it contains through The method of paradox, and this is what we also notice in its deepest manifestations in the saying of IbnZaydun by hereditary judge Abu Bakr bin Dhakwan when he says (48)

Who is for the dew if his family quarrels, and his meek ignorant people ignore it?

In this house charged with great tension, we find IbnZaydun succeeding once again in exploiting a very complex and significant societal image represented in the power of the ignorant and empowering them not because they possess the logical components of power in terms of lofty and wisdom, but rather for another matter related to their ability to inflict ignorance on the owners of the dream, the solution and the contract, and this matter It is often involved in councils in various eras and times, as IbnZaydun was able to sense this eternal paradox through his use of the concepts (ignorance / dream) in one place, and the researcher believes that the social / psychological / anthropological basis for this paradox gives it a great deal of novelty and the ability to extend He wants to shed light on the ability of people with different minds For a mature woman to reach the ranks of the wise, through a paradox that is both important and strange at the same time. Once again, IbnZaydun knocks on the door of eternity to produce for us a paradox of a special kind whose image is completed by describing that age, which has an eternal character, with contradictory qualities, as he says (49)

Forever my dictation is an eloquent non-Arab who gives my credit what I do not know, so I know

The one who predestined the accidents is equal to him the witness of them is sterility.

In this witness, we find IbnZaydun making eloquence in opposition to illiteracy and ignorance in opposition to knowledge and witnessing in opposition to bitterness in the chapter on praising the trusted Caliph and defaming his enemies. That he is accused of it, namely, the impermanence of his conditions, his fluctuation and his change from one issue to another, as he may be eloquent and non-verbal at the same time, just as knowledge in some of its chapters, as Eternity shows us, may come from ignorance Accidents of eternity in some of its pathways may equate between bitter, unbearable gallbladder and desirable sweet honey. The matter is repeated in his saying (50)

Did you not know that eternity gives after withholding?

How much a person has been harmed is something you thought would benefit.

In these two verses, IbnZaydun asks, interrogating him through his statement that eternity itself, in its fluctuating conditions, gives and prevents to the extent that it causes people some confusion in the concepts they adopt, so they do not differentiate between what harms them and benefits them through a continuous process of illusion that is woven by time, only where IbnZaydun finds his way to show the paradox The wonder that disappears under the folds of time and causes a revolution in the scales and the agreed upon axioms. (He does not wonder (how much) is not interrogative but declarative, he tells us in a paradoxical form)

Tributaries of constructing the paradoxical style in the poetry of IbnZaydun Al-Andalus

The student of the poetic production of IbnZaydun finds that one of the most important tributaries from which the poet drew the material of his poetic paradoxes are:

First: the natural tributary

The poetry of nature is ancient in our Arabic literature. The poets knew it in the form in which their Bedouin environment inspired them, so they contemplated nature and were fascinated by it and spread their pain and shared it in their sorrows and concerns. Andalusia is a large island in which there is abundant and adventurous... it is dominated by running water, trees, and abundance in all circumstances." (51) Therefore, we find that poets have been drawn to its source, and their hearts have been enamored with its beauty, and their souls have been fascinated by its love until it has become a man for themselves, a sweetness to their souls and an inexhaustible source for their poetry. IbnZaydun is considered one of the most prominent poets who employed nature by their notification, as they eagerly embraced it, flirting with its descriptions and depicting its charms, until nature became in his poetry with symbols and connotations that point to a deeper world that can be understood through the self and the paradoxes that filter out of it, especially those that came in his depiction of his relationship to the birth of a girl Al-Mustaqfi and the implications/paradoxes surrounding that relationship, so the researcher finds that nature has a clear presence in his poems.

O you who harmonize night and day, for the good between them is luminous and dark

In this verse, IbnZaydun establishes the researchers' conviction of his ingenuity in dealing with contradictions, as he deals with the concept of (harmony) in a completely different way, so he uses it to refer not to things that are harmonious and harmonious in nature, but to find a kind of rapprochement and reconciliation between representations of very different and different semantic natures, so the poet and in order to produce his own paradox He tells us this time - through nature - that his lover has a special feature or ability to combine contradictions, as she has the ability to agree with him between night / darkness / remission / blackness and day / light / whiteness / pursuit, where IbnZaydun performs in a distinct intellectual and linguistic maneuver to construct a paradox whose material is that Birth with its unique beauty that combines in one place light and darkness, and the researcher believes that the plastic dimension in this witness is strong, as the poet seems this

time aware of the importance of the color dimension in the poem, so he seems to be holding the tools of light that are common in the theatrical scene to show an image of birth through the paradox method as it moves Between light and dark in a unique way. In another place, the researcher encounters a poetic witness replete with connotations based on the problem of light and darkness in its crystallization, as IbnZaydun says in a poem he sent to Birth, bemoaning what was between them, as he says (53)

We lost you our days, so they turned black, and our nights were white for you

The poet, as we can see, is fully aware of what the process of approaching (comparison) produces between two types of semantic patterns of paradoxes and highly sensitive plastic images. IbnZaydun declares that the loss of a birth turns the white color that covers the bright days into a dark one, in order to demonstrate through the shocking color formation on the meaning of loss through A linguistic / semantic paradox that seems exceptional by all standards, and perhaps this exceptionality becomes more apparent when the poet says that the arrival of a birth in the past was turning the black nights into a space filled with bright light. The process of showing black and white colors or the concepts of light and darkness within a linguistic / plastic painting whose material was derived from the data of nature is one of the paradoxes whose study may lead to adding a new threshold from the thresholds of studying the paradox method, which is that employing the plastic dimension can help the text maker in formulating paradoxes TFill the mind and eye of the recipient. We see that the poet does not depart from nature in its various manifestations in his quest to produce paradoxes that appear to be a means to reach his purposes. He moves to another word from the vocabulary of nature, which is a paradox inspired by the scenes of nature and its wonderful paintings, as he says (54)

Al-Ghourabi Al-Walid has creatures like a garden, the laughter of the crying clouds

The poet in this place takes a funny path to praise the Caliph, so he enters the Nature Museum with his pictures, connotations, and beautiful scenes, and all this is in pursuit of an amazing paradox. Like a vast field laughing when quenched by the tears of a crying cloud / rain, where we find that the poet has succeeded brilliantly attesting to him by marrying two opposing concepts of laughter / crying, as he makes a semantic deal between them that takes place within the poetic scene. Essentially tributaries of the paradox if he spoke brilliantly. In order for the researcher to demonstrate the legitimacy of al-Rukun to consider nature, with its various vocabulary and its own dictionary, an important tributary of IbnZaydun's formulation of the paradox method, he refers to the poet's repeated use of the words (fire / water, cold / migration) to produce a poetic image that often serves him in his quest to flirt with his lover and to praise his praise and get closer to them And receiving their gifts, we see him saying (55)

The days have earned him the coolness of the air, for he is a body that has formed fire and water

We also find him saying, flirting with birth (56)

Patience is witness when you swallowed me, and fire is cold when you prayed for me

In these two places we see IbnZaydun constructing his poetic image on the foundations of nature as he formulates a contrast between two opposing sides, which are fire and water. The medicine that he gifted to his praise, which crowns him with distinction and uniqueness, and in the second place, the poet uses fire / ignition / combustion, water / extinguishing / gentleness to describe the love he feels for the birth of the beacon of love that he feels is nothing but cold and peace because its source is his beloved, which he sees only Everything that is beautiful and unique, even if her waiting has passed, turns into sweet tasting witness, as long as its source is the birth of the Al-Mustakfi's daughter.

Second, the religious stream

Religious belief is an important tributary of the tributaries that provided poets with the experience necessary to invent poetic images that are derived from the Holy Qur'an. The Qur'anic text has an advantage over the poetic text, including the distinctive style and precise expression of the Qur'anic text, the accuracy of its composition, the specificity of its music, and the depth of its connotations that tempt the poet to rely on him for his realization It will give the text strength in influence, credibility, and a complex symbolic intensity that splits into two pillars. The first is the symbolism of the Qur'anic text itself, which the text contains, and the second is that the religious text, when mentioned in the poetic text, imbibes this text with a kind of familiarity because the religious text is close to the psyche of the recipient (57). The poets differed in their access to the eyes of the religious stream. It seems that this is due to the extent of the poet's ability to employ the religious influence according to a context in which the glimpse is full of reference, announcing the birth of a new, lively vision (58) IbnZaydun is one of the poets who drew inspiration from the Noble Qur'an in word and meaning, and he took from it a specific one from which he derives the vocabulary of his poetic paradox. The first level: Preserving the structural form of the Qur'anic text with meaning and content, as the Qur'anic structure included in its poetic paradox preserved its significance without changing. The paradox resulting from the connotations of the Qur'anic text and this is what we find in his saying (59)

I do not repent sincerely from your love, God only punishes a lover who repents

In this witness, we find the poet was faithful to the Qur'anic discourse through a formalistic drawing par excellence, as he draws the sacred text by drawing and building it, despite our knowledge of his full bet on what the text itself can release from the indications that establish the method of paradox, which is a paradox that is

not based primarily on the linguistic/formal building, but rather It derives its value from the process of paradox of meaning, so the poet's repentance is an insincere repentance for the reason that God Almighty does not repent of the lovers who declare their repentance for love. Satisfaction, we find this matter repeated here as well. The poet, in order to achieve the greatest extent of astonishment, uses the Qur'anic text to reach the desired goal, although we know that he can do that through another way, but he chose to say the truth, the Most High, in the verse. "O you who have believed, repent to God in sincere repentance, perhaps your Lord will atone for your sins" (60) In our opinion, this is a reason to examine how religious discourse is represented to support the poetic vision, and this is what we find that IbnZaydun has succeeded in. The researcher finds that IbnZaydun remains preoccupied with using the Qur'anic dictionary to achieve his poetic purpose. He frequents this field in BabPraise when he says in praise of Al-Mu'tamid bin Abbad (61)

Aren't you the one who gets tired of an accident from which the face turns white and the chest expands?

In this witness, we find the poet based on two of the Qur'anic paths, which are the path of the text / the linguistic structure, with its connotations. The method of paradox, and as we have indicated in previous places, he only takes this path with the intention of astonishment and speed of influence. The poet has according to what he wanted when he invested the saying of the Most High And when Our Messengers came to a wicked lot with them, and he was fed up with them, and he said, "This is a difficult day." (62) IbnZaydun has created a strange contrast in what we see between the tightness of the chest and the brightening of the face, as the paradoxical method that he adopted can allow the recipient of the text to expect that the chest and the lightness of the face will be the result of narrowness and bitterness. The second level: IbnZaydun resorted to another technique by leaning his poetic paradox on the Qur'anic text without preserving the Qur'anic expressive structure. To reach the reader through the religious discourse / the Noble Qur'an, as in his saying (63)

You have made me commit the sin that you have come to believe, so forgive me, you sinner

The poet in this place declares that he is only asking for forgiveness and forgiveness from the one who committed the sin, and he is his lover, to give birth to the daughter of Al-Mustakfi. And to point out that the poet - in order to reach this level of intelligent foundation of the paradox method - has relied on the semantic dimension of the concept of forgiveness and forgiveness, which the researcher sees as a concept with Qur'anic roots that cannot be ignored, mentioned by the Holy Qur'an in his saying: "We did not create the heavens and the earth and what is between them except with truth. The hour to come, I will pardon the beautiful pardon" (64) and the Almighty's saying: "And if you pardon, pardon, and forgive, then God is Oft-Forgiving, Most Merciful" (65) and this is repeated in the words of IbnZaydun (66)

Your ransom is that my heart has melted from complaining to an inanimate heart

As we find the poet exploits the connotations filtering from the Almighty's saying, "Then their hearts hardened after that, so they are like stones or more hard" (67) to build a poetic paradox that shocks the reader. At birth, his heart had melted into inanimateness, similar to stones in hardness and hardness.

The third level

This is what is known as the technique of pointing and allusion, and it manifests itself in the ability of IbnZaydun Al-Andalus to employ the Qur'anic impact according to contexts in which the creative ability is crowded with religious reference to enrich his new work, announcing the birth of a new vision. This appears in his saying (68)

I will love my enemies, for you are one of them who keeps his frying healthy and makes him sick.

Here, the poet creates a paradox of a special style, as he declares that he will give his enemies love, that is, he draws a strange equation with two opposite ends, namely love / enmity, which leads him together with the reader / recipient of the speech to the highest that we can imagine about the paradox method and the picture is complete when IbnZaydun says that my eyes The birth of the two beauties gives the living sick health at the same time, and the researcher believes that a deeper reading of this poetic image will allow us to say that IbnZaydun was not at all strange about the method of paradox, whose features are complete for him in this month through a transparent and semi-hidden representation of the Qur'anic text represented in the Almighty's saying: (So if the one between you and him is enmity, it is as if he were an intimate guardian) (69). At this level, the poet's ingenuity and ability to beg the potentials of the recipient with his mental presence appears in the process of observing the phenomena of the poetic image, analyzing its features, and revealing its references, when a Qur'anic surah with its great meanings lies in a scene that forms a poetic image. The poet embodied it in his poetry, as in his saying (70)

You made me free after you boiled me and put me down and always raised me

In this place, the researcher can sense, even in a transparent way, the Qur'anic influence in the formulation of the poet's general/mental perceptions, which provided him with the ability to produce a very clear paradox, as we find him comparing (the cheapness / high stature), (lowness / high status) to refer to the influence of the beloved On it, and it is an image that IbnZaydun derived its roots from and from a hidden side from the Almighty's saying: "Oh God, you are the owner of the kingdom. Thirdly, the subjective stream: Just as culture and the environment interfere in shaping the poetic image of the poet, invoking it to be a source from which he draws at the moment of saying, the poet's interaction with the events he is going through and his response to

them negatively and positively affects the characteristics of his art and is considered another source that provides him with poetic images (72). The researcher that any deep study of the biography of IbnZaydun Al-Andalus, whether in the door of his love for birth or in the field of his relations with the general environment, will realize the importance of examining the self-dimension as a generator of many precursors that stemmed from the anxious and unstable life of this poet, especially in the field of his relationship with birth, which is the relationship that was drawn So many dimensions of his personality that, by broadcasting his psychological feelings to his lover, he reveals many of his personal secrets and psychological tendencies with a social dimension. In order to demonstrate the uniqueness of his fondness for childbirth, he chose the paradox as a method to convey what he wants, whether to his lover or the recipient, as the connoisseur of all aesthetic qualities produced by the poetic saying. Al-Tana'i has become a substitute for our condemnation, and he is a substitute for Tayyib for Quqayana, who has evaded us.

No, it was dawn between us and we were awake for a while.

The time that still makes people laugh near them has returned to cry us.

The anger of the enemy from our passions, they prayed that we suffocate, and he said, "Amen".

So what was bound to ourselves was dissolved, and what was bound by our hands sprouted.

And we may be, and we are not afraid to separate, for today we are and we are not expected to meet

In this poem, we see that the poet has cleverly and cleverly accomplished the task of accessing the world of semantics filtering from the opposition between opposites, where we find (the distance / the close, the meeting / the rendezvous, the laughter / the crying, the alignment / the dive, the solution / the knot, the cut / the connection, the parting, the convergence). Which gives us the opportunity to point out two essential things, the first is that this poem may be an objective example of a poet's ability to mobilize the largest amount of linguistic and semantic contradictions in one place. The second thing is that this piece can represent a scout that illuminates the self-producing text and begins to hold it accountable, along with the psychological and social foundations that prompted the poet to say what he was. Its summary is that the poet, despite the brightness of his work / being overwhelmed with sensuality of things / pleasure, at one point tries to provide an inventory of his own suffering, as he says: (74)

So what was tied to ourselves dissolved, and what was attached to our hands grew

In this verse, the poet implicitly refers to his personal responsibility for what happened to him with his birth, which is truly a complete paradox. In a kind of permanence, as it can be suitable for martyrdom by all those who see that the time that made them laugh one day is the same time that keeps them crying and raining tears from their eyes. As far as the fluctuations known about him, here is the poet who loses his beloved weeps. Perhaps this fluctuation and tendency to paradox is not limited to time. Rather, we find the poet himself, through his psychological crisis, inclined to a form of implicit paradox that he refers to in his saying (75)

No, and the morning has come, our morning is a while, so he stood up for us for a while

The poet, while presenting a self-confession of an intentional love, uses the reference to death in a way that is not without a strange paradox. He talks about the morning with its connotations that refer to birth and light and associates it with death with the meanings of sadness, separation and darkness, so he uses the phrase (Sobh Al-Bayan) which looks at the poet and responds to him The time is in the noun, which is the matter, which, as we see it, is a distinct use of the method of paradox in a unique form of its images, because in the end it drops a curtain on the journey of love. The soul meets another after separation and distance is what characterizes the last scene of his relationship with the birth of the daughter of Al-Mustakfi, and we find him in another place complaining about the cruelty of giving birth with him, when he says: (76) I find that the one whom I desire in love has tampered with, and I will fulfill the covenant to him, as he is in breach.

A lover who has distanced himself from me with closeness and sorrow resides in his deepest heart

In this place, IbnZaydun presents a very clear inventory of himself. Through the paradoxical method generated by the contrast between the concepts of grandfather, play, loyalty, indifference, distance and proximity, he indicates that his lover meets all his seriousness and poise with a lot of absurdity and indifference, and at the same time she meets his loyalty with a violation Promises and non-compliance with them, and the researcher believes that the most essential thing that we can feel about IbnZaydun is that the poet built his poetic intention on the foundations of a fortunate subjective nature, which is that he is a person characterized by seriousness and loyalty, and here the paradoxical style is born, which we previously indicated that it derives from the interview Among the antonyms, here it becomes a means to dedicate the same lover / serious in exchange for the same lover / frivolous, and we see that this is a successful use of the self as a tributary of the construction of the paradox method. Cruel to the self reveals the depth of what he suffers as he expresses his love for birth, as he says (77)

How much I want and what I want, O bad, what has found the heart

Wydad was purified, spoiled, from whom wydad did not describe me

The poet, in a strange manifestation, makes a difference within himself between that (he wants) and that (he does not want), and he reveals the bad and darkest of what happened to his heart, and he deals with the phases of passion with the birth of the daughter of Al-Mustakfi. Recognizing the ability of the self in its positive and

negative parts, being and non-being to produce the paradox method, which IbnZaydun touches in this witness in order to express the deep tension that afflicted him as a result of preventing a child from being a lover who responds to what her lover wants. In another example, the researcher encounters a unique model that is extremely simple and complex at the same time. To demonstrate the richness of the subjective resource and its ability to help the poet/text maker to create a poetic paradox of great depth and significance that clearly points to two issues, the first of which is the poet's anxiety and tension, and the second is the depth of his fascination with the birth of Al-Mustaqfi's daughter, as he says (78)

When will I tell you what is wrong with me, my comfort and my torment?

When will my tongue turn in explaining my book?

Here the poet sets up a confrontation between two subjective matters that have their origin in the depth of his subjective being, namely comfort and torment. It is covered here in a paradoxical style, and it is the method that the researcher sees as the only means available to the poet to express what he feels from the desire to broadcast what is in his sorrows and to inform his beloved of the sadness and pain within him.

Conclusion

The researcher believes - after completing the methodological requirements of his modest study (the paradox in the poetry of IbnZaydunAndalusi) - that he may have revealed a very novel and exceptional topic that the researchers had not dealt with before, so he put his hand on an essential joint that must be studied to draw a true picture On the Andalusian literature in general, where it was found that the study and analysis of the paradox in IbnZaydun's poetry can provide researchers with a real picture of the total mental/social perceptions that draw poetic images.

1. Paradox represents a stylistic stimulus and an element of creativity that works to supplement and develop the creative process. At the level of (poetry, poet, recipient) at the level of poetry, it represents a stylistic means that produces poetry and enriches it with semantics, images and imaginings. On the level of the poet, the poet's understanding of its structure and stylistic effect enables him to Seeing what he did not see before, it gives the poet who acquires it and forms it a kind of uniqueness and distinction.
2. The researcher found that the linguistic definition of paradox refers to the meaning of separation and divergence, which we did not find in the Qur'anic text 0 (verify)
3. Through the conventional definition of the concept of paradox, I find that many researchers focus on the use of the concept more than on the exact linguistic meaning, as they found that the daily conceptual use may be prior to the term paradox.
4. The Western critics have worked hard to find a clear meaning of an inferential nature of the concept of paradox, which has clearly and clearly affected the adoption of the modern Arab critics of the concept of paradox.
5. The researcher believes that Arab and Western critics have bet heavily on the role of the recipient in adopting the data that refer to the paradox method, which depends largely on the collection of contradictions in a deliberate and planned manner in literary texts.
6. The biography of the poet IbnZaydun, with its personal, psychological, political and emotional data, could be an important basis for researchers to find out the reasons behind the poet's apparent tendency to use the method of paradox to reach his poetic purpose. Poets in terms of being dependent on the method of paradox to reach his goals
7. The researcher believes that the poet's love for birth and the anxiety, tension and fluctuations surrounding this relationship have cast a shadow on the way in which IbnZaydun formulated the paradoxical style.
8. The researcher found that IbnZaydun's involvement in the Andalusian political life, and the relationships that that life created and produced from conspiracies and intrigues, dyed the poet's life a certain color, and that this life had a clear impact on his poetic achievement, in which the paradox was a living part of it, as IbnZaydun crossed Expressing his political concern by choosing the paradox as a method of expression.
9. Despite the quantitative modesty of IbnZaydun's poetic achievement, he was able to enable researchers to categorize several tributaries of the paradoxical method he adopted.
10. The researcher found, through his study of IbnZaydun's poetry, that he had employed nature to produce the paradox style, using the clear aesthetic characteristics of Andalusian geography.
11. By studying IbnZaydun's poetry, the researcher found something important and novel at the same time, which is the poet's tendency to evade a certain religious / Quranic effect, whether directly or indirectly in building his poetic paradox.
12. We find that IbnZaydun has derived some of his poetic paradoxes from his personal experience and psychological characteristics as the generator of many poetic images, especially that the poet lived an anxious and unstable life, whether in his emotional experience with the birth of the daughter of Al-Stakfi or in his relationship with the political and social environment at that time.

margins

1. See: Lisan Al Arab: Article (Farq): 10/299

2. Paradox in Arabic poetry: 29
3. See: Paradox and its attributes (Encyclopedia of Critical Terms): 27
4. See: Same source: 29
5. See: same source: 29
6. See: Paradox Theory: 57
7. See: Same source: 57
8. See: The Paradox in the Poetry of Abu Nawas (Master Thesis): 14
9. See: The Qur'anic Paradox, A Study in the Structure of Significance: 15
10. See: Paradox Theory: 56
11. The concept of paradox (Fusoul Magazine): 132
12. Paradox in Al-Mutanabbi's Poetry (Journal of the College of Education for Girls): 2
13. See: Deaths of Al-A'yan: 1/139, Maghrib: 1/63
14. See: Features of Andalusian Poetry: 133
15. See: IbnZaydun, his age, life and literature: 64
16. See: Al-Bayan Al-Maghrib: 3/185
17. See: History of Arabic literature (the era of the kings of the sects): 4/592
18. See: Andalusian literature, development and renewal: 489
19. See: History of Arabic literature (the era of the kings of the sects): 4/593
20. Diwan: 265
21. Same source: 18
22. See: Features of Andalusian Poetry: 134
23. See: Same source: 134-135
24. See: History of Arabic literature (the era of the kings of the sects): 4/593
25. See: The deaths of notables: 1/139
26. See: Al-Thakhira: 1/387
27. See: same source: 1/380
28. See: Features of Andalusian Poetry: 136
29. Diwan: 94
30. Same source: 46, 57
31. Ammo: 1/380
32. Same source: 1/279
33. See: History of Arabic literature (the era of the kings of the sects): 4/591
34. Diwan: 62
35. Same source: 65
36. Same source: 56
37. Same source: 283
38. Same source: 25
39. Same source: 258
40. Same source: 190
41. Same source: 23
42. Same source: 105
43. Same source: 106
44. Same source: 134-135
45. Same source: 247
46. Same source: 81
47. Same source: 132
48. Same source: 188
49. Same source: 273
50. Same source: 256
51. Dictionary of countries: 1/262
52. Diwan: 62
53. Diwan: 10
54. Same source: 98
55. Same source: 281
56. Same source: 66
57. See: The symbol and its significance in the poetry of Andalusian women: 15
58. See: Abu Tamar his life through his poetry: 11
59. Diwan: 77
60. Surah At-Tahrim: 8
61. Diwan: 18

62. Hur: Verse 77
63. Diwan: 53
64. Surah: Al-Hijr: 85
65. Surah: Al-Taghabun: 14
66. Diwan: 24
67. Surah Al-Baqarah: 74
68. Diwan: 62
69. Surah: Fussilat: 34
70. Diwan: 66
71. Surah 71: Al Imran: 26
72. See: The Psychological Foundations of Lhasa for the Heart of Arabic Rhetoric: 247
73. Diwan: 9
74. Same source: 9
75. Same source: 9
76. Same source: 73
77. Same source: 51
78. Same source: 50

Sources and references

The Holy Quran

1. IbnZaydun, his age, life and literature, Abdel Azim Ali, Al-Shorouk Press, 1st ed., Cairo: 1967
2. Abu Tammam His Life through His Poetry, NajibBahiti, Dar Al-Fikr, Al-Khanji Library: 1970
3. Andalusian literature, development and renewal, d. Abdel Moneim Al-Khafaji, Dar Al-Jeel, Beirut, Dr. T
4. The psychological foundations of the methods of Arabic rhetoric, Dr. Majid Abdel Hamid Naji, University Foundation for Studies, Publishing and Distribution, Beirut, Edition 1, 1984:
5. Al-Bayan Al-Maghrib in the news of Andalusia and the Maghreb, by IbnAdhari Al-Marrakchi (695 d), tahKulan and Revensal, House of Culture, Beirut (d. T).
6. A history of Arabic literature to the last kings of the sects, Omar Farroukh, Dar Al-Ilm for Millions, 1, Beirut, 1983.
7. DiwanIbnZaydoun, Explanation and Investigation of Karam Al-Bustani, Dar Sader Beirut, 3rd Edition: 2007
8. Al-Dhakhira in the merits of the people of the island, IbnBassam Al-Shantarini, Al-Ahram Press, Cairo: 1945 AD.
9. Lisan Al-Arab, IbnManzur, prepared and classified by Youssef Al-Khayat and NadimMaraachli, Lisan Al-Arab Cultural House, Beirut, 1991.
10. Mu'jam Al-Buldan, Shihab Al-Din Yaqout Al-Hamawi, corrected by Muhammad Amin Al-Khanji Al-Saada Press, Egypt, 1916 AD.
11. The Paradox in the Poetry of AbiNawas, Karrar Abdul-Ilah Al-Ibrahimi, Master Thesis, College of Education for Human Sciences, University of Al-Muthanna: 2017.
12. Paradox in modern Arabic poetry, d. Nasser Shabana, The Arab Foundation for Studies and Publishing, Beirut, 1st edition, 2007 AD.
13. The Qur'anic Paradox, A Study in the Structure of Semantics, Dr. Muhammad Al-Abd, Library of Arts, Cairo, Egypt, 2nd Edition: 2006 AD
14. Paradox and its attributes (Encyclopedia of Critical Terminology): DC Moywick, translated by Abdul WahedLulua, Dar Al-Mamoun for Translation and Publishing, Baghdad, 2nd Edition, 1987 AD.
15. Features of Andalusian Poetry, Dr. Omar Dakkak, Dar Al-Sharr Publications, Beirut, 1984 AD.
16. The Deaths of Notables, Son Khalkan, investigation by Muhammad Muhyi al-Din Abd al-Hamid, Cairo, 3rd edition 1948

Magazines

1. The symbol and its significance in the poetry of the Andalusian woman, d. MunirObaidNajm Journal of the College of Basic Soil, University of Babylon, No. 17, 2016
 2. The Paradox in the Poetry of Al-Mutanabi, Abdul HadiKhudair, Journal of the College of Education for Girls, Issue (11) 2000 AD.
 3. The concept of paradox, Fosoul magazine: Volume 7, Issue 4, 1987 AD.
- Paradox Theory Khaled Suleiman: Volume 9 Number 2 Yarmouk University / 1991 AD.

Author Information

Dr.. Munir Obaid NajmCollege Of Basic Education / University Of Babylon
